

TRADE DIPLOMACY BETWEEN THE KHIVATE OF KHIVA AND FOREIGN STATES

Teacher of the Department of History, Mamun University

Rakhimberganov Jo'rabek Otanazar o'g'li

rakhimberganovjorabek@gmail.com

+998937455575

Abstract. This article covers the trade relations of the Khiva Khanate with foreign countries, their formation, stages of development and content. In particular, trade relations with countries such as the Russian Empire, Iran, Afghanistan, and India are analyzed based on historical sources. The article studies the caravan routes, customs policy, the political and economic impact of trade relations, as well as the activities of foreign merchants in the Khiva region. The positive and negative impact of foreign trade on the economy of the Khiva Khanate, as well as the impact of trade relations on international diplomatic relations, are also analyzed. The study serves to further understand the economic role of the Khiva Khanate in the history of Central Asia.

Keywords: India, caravan routes, trade relations, customs policy, merchants, trade diplomacy, export and import, handicraft products, Khiva caravan markets, foreign economic policy, trade competition,

Central Asian trade system, 19th century Khiva economy, border trade, international relations, foreign merchants.

XIVA XONLIGI VA CHET DAVLATLAR O'RTASIDAGI SAVDO DIPLOMATIYASI

Ma'mun universiteti "Tarix" kafedrasi o'qituvchisi

Raximberganov Jo'rabek Otanazar o'g'li

rakhimberganovjorabek@gmail.com

+998937455575

Annatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Xiva xonligining chet davlatlar bilan savdo aloqalari, ularning shakllanishi, rivojlanish bosqichlari va mazmun-mohiyati yoritilgan. Xususan, Rossiya imperiyasi, Eron, Afg'oniston, Hindiston kabi mamlakatlar bilan tuzilgan savdo munosabatlari tarixiy manbalar asosida tahlil qilingan. Maqolada karvon yo'llari, bojxona siyosati, savdo aloqalarining siyosiy va iqtisodiy ta'siri, shuningdek, chet ellik savdogarlarning Xiva hududidagi faoliyati o'rganiladi. Tashqi savdoning Xiva xonligi iqtisodiyotiga ko'rsatgan ijobiy va salbiy ta'siri, hamda savdo aloqalarining xalqaro diplomatik munosabatlarga ta'siri ham tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot Markaziy Osiyo tarixida Xiva xonligining iqtisodiy o'rnini yanada chuqurroq anglashga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Hindiston, karvon yo'llari, savdo aloqalari, bojxona siyosati, savdogarlar, savdo diplomatiyasi, eksport va import, hunarmandchilik mahsulotlari, Xiva karvonbozorlari, tashqi iqtisodiy siyosat, savdo raqobati, Markaziy Osiyo savdo tizimi, XIX asr Xiva iqtisodiyoti, chegara savdosi, xalqaro aloqalar, xorijiy savdogarlar.

The Khiva Khanate was one of the most important trading centers of Central Asia in the 16th-20th centuries, and it widely developed foreign trade relations. Although the Khanate's trade relations were mainly with the Russian state and the countries of Central Asia, there is also sufficient information about its trade with other cities in Europe and Asia.

It is known that the Khiva Khanate's foreign relations with Europe were mainly through Iran, the Ottoman Empire, and the Caspian Sea route. Trade with India and China was carried out through the mediation of Bukhara or other peoples. The Transcaucasian Silk Road, located at the crossroads of trade routes connecting the East with Europe since ancient times, retained its importance in international transit trade even after losing its transcontinental potential. The Caucasus region was often mentioned in contemporary sources as a bridge between Europe and Asia¹. During this period, the activities of Central Asian merchants in Iran and the Transcaucasus did not cease. In the 17th century, Iran, the Transcaucasus, the Ottoman Empire, and Europe were connected to major trading centers by the trade route Akulis-Nakhichevan-Yerevan-Kars-Arzirum-Toqat-Izmir-Istanbul-Venice-Frankfurt-Dusseldorf-Amsterdam.²

According to the testimony of E. Kempfer, a German resident who came to Russia in the 17th century, merchant ships from Russia, Circassia, Dagestan, "Uzbekistan" and Iran were anchored in a quiet bay on the coast of Baku³. Salt, oil, and fruits brought here on small merchant ships were transported to "Uzbekistan" and neighboring cities⁴. In the 16th-17th centuries, Shemakha traded not only with cities in the Transcaucasus region, but also with cities in Central Asia, Russia, and Western Europe. There were seven caravanserais around the city, where Russian, Tatar, and European merchants, as well as Tajik and Uzbek merchants, traded⁵. The city of Shemakha was a meeting place for merchants traveling to the Moscow state, Sweden, and Holland. For this reason, the number of people coming and going to this city was very large.⁶

In the 16th and 17th centuries, silk trade played an important role in Shemakha's internal and external trade. During this period, the city became a base for Russian and European trade with the East, and there was a permanent English merchant court in the city⁷. In turn, the entry of English industrial goods into the markets of Bukhara and Khiva was facilitated through court merchants. The appearance of English merchants in Bukhara and Khiva via the Caucasus was disturbing to the Russian government.⁸

By the end of the 17th and beginning of the 19th centuries, the import of oriental goods to European countries by various means increased. Karakul furs and carpets were imported from Khiva and Bukhara to Iran, the main export of which was through the Ottoman lands to Europe. Large quantities of turquoise and Shiraz sheepskin were imported from Iran⁹. Carpet weaving was developed in the Turkmen lands of the Bukhara and Khiva Khanates. Turkmen carpets were highly

¹ Киняпина Н.С., Блиев М. М., Дегоев В.В Кавказ И Средняя Азия во внешней политике России. (Вторая половина XVIII-80-е годы XIX в.) – М., 1984. – С. 4.

² Дневник Закария Акулского. – Ереван.,1939. – С. 6.

³ Ашурбейли С.Б Очерки истории средневекового Баку. – Баку., 1964. – С. 216.

⁴ Ашурбейли С.Б Очерки истории средневекового Баку. – Баку., 1964. – С. 216.

⁵ Джидди Г.А. Средневековой город Шемаха IX-XVII вв, –Баку.:Элм. 1981. – С. 108.

⁶ Алиев Ф.М Место Азербайджана в международной транзитной торговле в XVIII в // Материалы по экономической истории Азербайджана (К В международному конгрессу экономической истории). – Баку.: Элм, 1970. – С. 60.

⁷ Джидди Г.А. Средневековой город Шемаха IX-XVII вв – Баку.: Элм. 1981. – С. 108.

⁸ Киняпина Н.С., Блиев М.М., Дегоев В.В Кавказ и Средняя Азия во внешней политике России. (Вторая половина XVIII-80-е годы XIX в.) – М., 1984. – С. 4.

⁹ Валиева Д.В. Среднеазиатско-иранские отношения в первой половине XIX века // Взаимоотношение народов Средней Азии и сопредельных стран Востока. – Т., 1963. – С. 52-53.

valued in Iran, Bukhara, and Khiva. From the beginning of the 19th century, Turkmen carpets were exported to Western European countries via Russia¹⁰. By the second half of the 19th century, European goods had become abundant in the khanate's markets. German Vambéry wrote that upon entering the first village in the Khiva Khanate, he was filled with joy upon seeing European-made goods there¹¹.

Khiva silk fabrics were often exported to Asian and European countries via transit trade routes. For this reason, in the 16th and 17th centuries, silk and silk fabrics from Iran and Central Asia were exported to Europe, to the Ottoman Empire, and from there to Europe¹².

In the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, a large number of English goods were imported to the Khorasan, Seistan, and Baluchistan regions of Iran. Along with English goods, large quantities of various fruits were imported from Iran to Khiva and Bukhara: pomegranates, oranges, lemons, plums, pistachios, and almonds¹³.

In order to establish their rule in Central Asia, the British intended, first of all, to establish economic relations with these territories and bring the Central Asian markets under British influence, and, on the other hand, to establish their rule there by squeezing them through diplomatic relations. British industrial goods first appeared in the Central Asian markets in 1825.¹⁴

V. Lugansky provides interesting information about British agents who, disguised as merchants, crossed into Khiva through Iran in the 1830s:

“In the spring of this year,” he writes, “five or seven Englishmen came to Khiva through Iran, led by Turkmens. They were said to be merchants, and Turkmen observers, having arranged with the Khiva rulers, brought them to Khiva, not to Bukhara. The Khan imprisoned them in one of the houses on the outskirts of the city, where they lay for a long time. Finally, on the day of Eid, they were released and walked around freely all day, but this was their last day of freedom. The next morning, these Englishmen were arrested, taken to the outskirts of the city, and tortured and interrogated in the presence of the Khan. They, however, said that they were going to Bukhara on business. But the Khan ordered them to be strangled to death before his eyes. The Khan’s officials immediately carried out his order. When two of them were left alive, one of the Khan’s herdsmen told him this said:

-Taksir, you see, they have no sin, otherwise they would confess their sins, what is the need to increase their sins in vain, let them go!

But the khan said: - After killing their comrades, what is the use of letting them go, when they see what is written on their foreheads, they must kill the rest, - the last of them cursed the khan severely and said: - As you have tortured us, soon you will also face such difficult times. The khan did not like this word, and the khan thought for a long time. It is said that 5,000 chervons were found in the wallets of these Englishmen¹⁵.

¹⁰ Бакасова Р. Из истории экономической мысли в Туркменистане в XVIII веке. – Ашхабад., 1981. – С. 74.

¹¹ Путешествия по Средней Азии совершенной в 1863 году Арманием Вамбери. – СПб., 1865. – С. 63.

¹² Валийева Д. XIX асрнинг биринчи ярмида Бухоро ва Хиванинг ташқи иқтисодий алоқаларига доир... – Б 165.

¹³ Логофет Д.Н. На границах Средней Азии, путевые очерки в 3-х книгах, книга 1. Русско-персидская граница. – СПб.: В.Березовский, 1909. – С. 237-238.

¹⁴ Рожкова М.К. Экономическая политика сарцкого правительства на Среднем Востоке во второй четверти XIX века и русская буржуазия. – М., 1949. – С. 219.

¹⁵ Из устного рассказа В. Луганского // С. Петербургские ведомости. – 1839. – №24. – С.164.

The trade relations of the country's cities, especially Khiva, with the East and the West are also confirmed by the coins of China, Russia, Germany, the Ottoman Empire, Afghanistan, and Iran found in its territory.¹⁶

Trade relations with foreign countries played an important role in the history of the Khiva Khanate, which left a certain mark on the economic development, political position and international relations of the khanate. Trade relations with the Russian Empire, Iran, Afghanistan and India turned the Khiva Khanate into an important economic bridge connecting the outside world.

Trade activities carried out through caravan routes led not only to the exchange of goods, but also to the expansion of cultural and diplomatic ties. Customs policy, free movement of merchants, the operation of safe roads and markets strengthened the foreign trade system of the Khiva Khanate, making it one of the most important economic centers in the region.

References

1. Киняпина Н.С., Блиев М. М., Дегоев В.В Кавказ И Средняя Азия во внешней политике России. (Вторая половина XVIII-80-е годы XIX в.) – М., 1984. – С. 4.
2. Дневник Закария Акулского. – Ереван., 1939. – С. 6.
3. Ашурбейли С.Б Очерки истории средневекового Баку. – Баку., 1964. – С. 216.
4. Ашурбейли С.Б Очерки истории средневекового Баку. – Баку., 1964. – С. 216.
5. Джидди Г.А. Средневековой город Шемаха IX-XVII вв, –Баку.:Элм. 1981. – С. 108.
6. Алиев Ф.М Место Азербайджана в международный транзитной торговле в XVIII в // Материалы по экономической истории Азербайджана (К В международному конгрессу экономической истории). – Баку.: Элм, 1970. – С. 60.
7. Джидди Г.А. Средневековой город Шемаха IX-XVII вв – Баку.: Элм. 1981. – С. 108.
8. Киняпина Н.С., Блиев М.М., Дегоев В.В Кавказ и Средняя Азия во внешней политике России. (Вторая половина XVIII-80-е годы XIX в.) – М., 1984. – С. 4.
9. Валиева Д.В. Среднеазиатско-иранские отношения в первой половине XIX века // Взаимоотношение народов Средней Азии и сопредельных стран Востока. – Т., 1963. – С. 52-53.
10. Бақасова Р. Из истории экономической мысли в Туркменистане в XVIII веке. – Ашхабад., 1981. – С. 74.
11. Путешествия по Средней Азии совершенной в 1863 году Арманием Вамбери. – СПб., 1865. – С. 63.
12. Валиева Д. XIX асрнинг биринчи ярмида Бухоро ва Хиванинг ташқи иқтисодий алоқаларига доир... – Б 165.
13. Логофет Д.Н. На границах Средней Азии, путевые очерки в 3-х книгах, книга 1. Русско-персидская граница. – СПб.: В.Березовский, 1909. – С. 237-238.

¹⁶ Ichon Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondi. KP1067, KP 1068, KP 1070, KP 1093, KP 1080, KP 1092, KP 1096, KP 1103, KP 1091, KP 1102, KP 1079, 1086, KP 1089, 1072, KP 1073, KP 1077, KP 1088. KP 1097, KP 1098, KP 1100, KP 1101.